

Systematic review on the conceptualizations of values

Recoding of records presenting evidence on “norms, rules, rights relative to valuation context (institutions)” to inform section 2.4

Statement	Questions	Options	Responses	OBS
A. Values are individual as well as shared. Certain values are common across a society and influence people’s identities. Values are typically embedded in institutions like norms and legal rules	General Type of Institution	Norms	1-0	
		Legal rules	1-0	
	Name and describe the specific institution		Open-ended question	
	The institution articulates	Intrinsic Values	1-0	
		Relational Values	1-0	
		Instrumental	1-0	
	Explain how the institution articulates the stated values		Open-ended question	
	The institution reflects the following worldview on human-nature relationships	Living from	1-0	
		Living in	1-0	
		Living with	1-0	
		Living as	1-0	
	Explain how the institution relates to the particular life-value frames		Open-ended question	
	The institution articulates plural values		No plurality	Explain
			Weak	Explain
			Strong	Explain
		self-regarding	1-0	Explain

	The institutions emphasizes the following rationality	others-regarding	1-0	Explain
		reciprocal	1-0	Explain
B. Institutions and their associated values may be contested, generating conflicts among social actors. What values are prioritized in a society is affected by power relations	Presence of conflicts related to institutions and their embedded values are addressed or mentioned		1-0	Explain
	Power relations related to the institutions and their embedded values are addressed or mentioned		1-0	Explain
	Explain which is the conflict and values at stake		Open-ended question	
H: <u>Acknowledging distributional implications of environmental policies are important to increase support for policies</u>	The paper recognizes that distributional implications of environmental policies or other institutions are important to increase support for policies:		1-0	if yes, explain
C. The influence of individually held values on behavior is often not very strong. What opportunities people face as well as what other people do explain to some extent the observed 'value-action-gap'.	The paper acknowledged that action/behavior or decision making is affected by	values, life-goals, motivations	1-0	Explain including the explanation of other if it is the case (open-ended question)
		individual's physical or psychological capacity	1-0	
		habits	1-0	
		Emotions	1-0	
		economic/financial restrictions	1-0	
		The opportunity allowed by the physical environment	1-0	
		The opportunity allowed by the cultural environment including what other people do (norms)	1-0	
		Power relations	1-0	
		Others	1-0	
D. Value expressions may be implicit in the decisions we make. They may also be explicitly expressed as statements. Valuation methods are used to facilitate such expressions.	Is there a relevant reference to a particular ivalue articulating nstitution aimed at value expression (i.e. valuation methods or decision-making approaches (e.g. Cost-benefit analysis, multicriteria assesment,etc) ?		1-0	
	The method was oriented to elicit:	Monetary Values	1-0	
		biophysical	1-0	

		Social/cultural values	1-0	
		Indegenous and Local people valuation approaches	1-0	
E: The type of method/value articulating institution used influences whose values are considered, how values can be expressed, and what value aspects become emphasized.	Is there a reflection on how the method/value articulating institution influences whose values are considered, how values can be expressed, and what value aspects become emphasized (reflexivity of valuation methods/institutions)		1-0	If yes, explain
F: Values influence public decision-making both through the routines (institutions) guiding such decisions as well as through consultations with the public. The way such consultations are made influences outcome	Is there a description of rules guiding decisions - e.g., decision-maker (like a public agency) has to follow certain predefined criteria?		1-0	If yes, explain
	Are these internally prioritized?		1-0	If yes, explain
	Rules regarding when consultations with the public are to be made. Are there any rules defining how consultations should be made?		1-0	If yes, explain
	Is there any focus on how these rules influence how the values of the public can be expressed?		1-0	If yes, explain
G: Activation of norms influence behavior. Environmental policy can become more effective by appealing to as well as by respecting such norms	The paper recognizes the policies and other Institutions (institutional changes or otherwise) can become more effective by appealing to as well as by respecting such norms		1-0	If yes, Explain
	The policy or institution	Emphasizes individuals/community values, life goals, norms	1-0	If yes, Explain
		Provide punishments	1-0	
		Provide rewards	1-0	
The addressed institution is related to TARGETED POLICY THEMES [TPT]	The institution is oriented to the following	TPT1: Diversity of values of nature and grassroots environmental movements. Expression/articulation of diversity of values in grassroots (environmental) movements associated with environmental conflicts	1-0	If yes, explain
		TPT2: Incorporation of the multiple values of nature into public and corporate accounting. Incorporation of the multiple values of nature into public and corporate accounting beyond accounting systems and performance indicators	1-0	
		TPT3: Diversity of values of nature in education for the future. The role of education (with	1-0	

		emphasis on young people) for catalysing multiple values inter-generationally		
		TPT4: Mainstreaming diverse values of nature in policies across ministries. How to mainstream multiple values of nature in policies across government ministries: Opportunities and challenges	1-0	
The addressed institution is related to GRAND CHALLENGES [GC]	The institution is oriented to the following	GC1: Rapid and/or large-scale land use transformations (choosing among the following: large infrastructure projects such as dams, large monoculture plantations, rapid urbanization processes)	1-0	If yes, explain
		GC2: Agriculture and food production (intensive vs. extensive, monoculture vs. agroecological, large scale vs. small farmers, corporations vs. IPLCs)	1-0	
		GC3: Unsustainable fisheries (small scale/artisanal vs. industrial, aquaculture vs. coastal/oceans)	1-0	
		GC4: "Fence and forget" or the use of protected areas for biodiversity conservation	1-0	